

KEMAMPUAN AWAL KALKULUS MAHASISWA PENDIDIKAN MATEMATIKA

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mendeskripsikan tingkat kemampuan awal Kalkulus mahasiswa Pendidikan Matematika FKIP Universitas Bung Hatta tahun pertama. Metode penelitian menggunakan metode deskriptif. Subjek penelitian adalah mahasiswa yang mengambil mata kuliah Kalkulus Diferensial pada semester kedua. Instrumen penelitian menggunakan tes *diagnostic* yang dikembangkan oleh Stewart dengan materi aljabar, Geometri, Trigonometri, dan Fungsi serta wawancara terhadap peserta. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis dekriptif. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, terlihat bahwa kemampuan awal mahasiswa berada pada tingkat sangat rendah, yaitu 8,6%. Hasil wawancara terhadap 6 orang mahasiswa yang mempunyai kemampuan skor tinggi, sedang, dan rendah menyatakan bahwa mahasiswa memerlukan tambahan pengetahuan tentang konsep bilangan serta sifat-sifatnya, operasi aljabar, visualisasi dengan teknologi serta konsep fungsi. Berdasarkan hasil tersebut, diperlukan strategi pembelajaran pada mata kuliah Kalkulus yang berbasis teknologi untuk memberi pemahaman konsep Kalkulus.

Kata Kunci: kemampuan awal, tingkat kemampuan awal, strategi pembelajaran.

Abstract

The research aimed to describe the initial ability level of Mathematics Education in the first year of the Mathematics Education Faculty of Bung Hatta University. The research method used descriptive. The research subjects were students who took Differential Calculus courses in the second semester. The research instrument used diagnostic tests developed by Stewart with algebraic material, Geometry, Trigonometry, and Functions as well as interviews with participants. Data analysis techniques used descriptive analysis. Based on the results of the research, it appeared that the initial ability of students is at a very low level, which is 8.6%. The results of interviews with 6 students who have the ability to score high, medium, and low stated that students need additional knowledge about the concept of numbers and their properties, algebraic operations, visualization with technology and the concept of functions. Based on these results, a learning strategy for technology-based Calculus is needed to provide an understanding of the Calculus concept.

Keywords: prior knowledge, grade of prior knowledge, learning strategy.